

STELLAR CLUSTERS IN THE MILKY WAY UNDER THE LENS OF GAIA AND ITS FRIENDS

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Star Clusters: the Gaia Revolution

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online, organised by the Institute of Cosmos Sciences (ICCUB-IEEC)

Friends of Gaia

(sorry for the personal bias)

- ▶ HST (for globular clusters)
& other space telescopes
- ▶ Large spectroscopic surveys (APOGEE, Gaia-ESO, GALAH, LAMOST, ...)
& the promise of the near future (WEAVE, MOONS, 4MOST, SDSS V, ...)
& the hope of future instruments/surveys (MSE, MAVIS, HRMOS, ...)
- ▶ Large photometric surveys (e.g. VPHAS+ for open clusters, ...)
- ▶ Asteroseismology (CoRoT, Kepler/K2, TESS, ...)
- ▶ Private, smaller projects (e.g. OCCASO, SPA, OSTTA for open clusters, FLAMES projects – Na,O anticorrelation, MiKis – MUSE for globulars, ...)

*(will try to avoid as much as possible what is presented elsewhere 🙅
and NO, not everything named above will be discussed here,
in particular, forget about photometry)*

Isn't Gaia all we need ?

Gaia, open clusters & spiral arms

Castro-Ginard+2021

RVs for fainter stars and clusters require ground-based spectroscopy
Abundances even more

Tarricq+2021

Will Gaia do it? The RVS

ESA/Gaia/DPAC-CU8, Recio-Blanco and the GSP-Spec team

A movie with several RVS spectra is visible as "Image of The Week" ([Gaia webpage](#))

Will Gaia do it? Radial velocities, metallicity, abundances

NGC6752 47Tuc M15 NGC2808

dist [kpc]=4.0 4.1 10.4 10.7

Vasiliev & Baumgardt 2021 for Gaia EDR3 membership

x-match with Gaia-ESO

What is in Gaia-ESO ?

- *115000 stars in: bulge, MW disk, local halo, 15 GCs, 80+ OCs*
[about 6500 observed with UVES U580, remaining with GIRAFFE multiple setups]
- *Precise RVs + $v \sin i$ (subsample)*
- *Stellar parameters [Teff, log g, metallicity + others for young clusters]*
- *Abundances: up to 23 for stars observed with GIRAFFE (e.g. Li, Mg, Al, etc)*
up to 35 for stars observed with UVES (e.g. C, N, Na, etc)
[depending on star type e.g. warm/cool and setup e.g. MW/OC]
- *Homogenization & validation : Gaia Benchmark stars + GCs + OCs + CoRoT, Kepler*
- *Solar reference values: internal [good match to Grevesse et al. 2007]*
- *X-matched with Gaia EDR3*

[all spectra (raw & reduced) already available at ESO archive; final catalog will soon be]

What is in Gaia-ESO? Open Clusters

- 62 Open Clusters *extensively* observed by Gaia-ESO (+existing ESO archive)
- ~20 directly retrieved from UVES-FLAMES archive

About 50% of Gaia-ESO time (340 VLT nights, with FLAMES) was dedicated to open clusters.

Observations in Dec 2011-Jan 2018, i.e. pre-Gaia DR2

What is in Gaia-ESO? Young clusters & Star Forming Regions (here NGC6530)

Age spread in the star forming region NGC6530 from the HR diagram and gravity indicators

→ SF began 15 Myr ago, but bulk was 1-2 Myr ago

[Prisinzano+2019](#)

Asymmetric expansion of the Lagoon Nebula cluster NGC6530 from GES and Gaia DR2

[Wright+2019](#)

What is in Gaia-ESO ? Atomic diffusion & stellar models

Evidence of atomic diffusion in M67?

[Bertelli-Motta+ 2018](#)

3D NLTE abundances in the open cluster NGC 2420 suggest atomic diffusion and turbulent mixing are at the origin of chemical abundance variations

[Semenova+ 2020](#)

What is in Gaia-ESO ? Lots of lithium

Mixing processes in low-mass stars traced by lithium abundance in cluster and field stars

Galactic evolution of lithium from iDR6

What is in Gaia-ESO ? 15 Globular Clusters in iDR6

Zn versus Fe

([Vasiliev & Baumgardt 2021](#) for Gaia EDR3 membership)

[Minelli+ 2021](#) : Sc, V, Zn \rightarrow accreted GCs ¹¹

And if you want more Globular Clusters: FLAMES

- Homogeneous database
 >2800 red giants (+HB)
- Quantitative study of multiple populations
- Na-O anticorrelation is “universal” in GCs
- Extension of anticorr. depends on mass (& max T_{eff} in HB)
 - ➔ Minimum GC mass for multiple populations
- C/N, O/Na, Mg/Al, also Si (rarely also K, Ca)
- Discrete groups in the anticorrelations
- Second generation stars have smaller binary %
- Li requires expansions and models
- Importance of (small) He differences

series of ~100 papers (2001 →) by E.Carretta, R.Gratton, AB, V.D’Orazi, S.Lucatello

And if you want more Globular Clusters: FLAMES

Mass is the (most) important property to produce and shape multiple populations – then age, metallicity (cf HST photometry, APOGEE, etc)

Precise abundance measures can separate populations (cf precise [UV] photometry)

And if you want more even more Globular Clusters (spectroscopy) ...

APOGEE: data for 40+ GCs in DR16 (Meszaros+2020 & see R. Schiavon's talk on breaking news)

→ has Fe, C, N, O, Mg, Al, K, alpha's, ...

Private datasets: with many instruments, by many researchers (limiting to recent years:

e.g. C. Johnson, A. Marino, D. Yong, A. Mucciarelli, E. Pancino, B. Barbuy, P. Bonifacio,

D. Geisler, A. Koch, H. Baumgardt ... and collaborators ...

and SORRY FOR THE MANY MISSING HERE)

→ large datasets on ω Cen, light elements variations, multiple populations, n-capture elements, intrinsic spreads in Fe and/or heavy elements, diffusion, etc etc

MUSE: a new actor in the field? (see e.g. Husser+2020; Kamann+2020a,b, 2021)

→ pro: Integral Field, reaches the inner GC regions (similar to HST); con: low resolution

New instruments: expect more from WEAVER, MOONS, 4MOST quite soon

GC people (borrowed from V. D'Orazi)

away from high-resolution spectroscopy for a while

LAMOST

LAMOST-LR
R = 1800
 369-910nm
 about 10M stars
 in DR6

Exploring open cluster properties with Gaia and LAMOST
 A few examples of the 295 clusters (and 8800 stars) in LAMOST DR5 – now DR6 is public and DR8 is available internally

Zhong J. + 2020

LAMOST Medium Resolution Spectroscopic Survey

LAMOST-MRS

R = 7000
495-535 +
630-680 nm
some million
stars
time-domain

Asteroseismology & stellar clusters

Region	Campaign	Super-stamp?	Region Type	Age Range [Gyr]	Extensively studied?
<i>Cody+ 2018</i>					
NGC 6819	Kepler prime	Y	open cluster	1–2	Y
NGC 6791	Kepler prime	Y	open cluster	~8	Y
NGC 6811	Kepler prime	N	open cluster	1–2	N
NGC 6866	Kepler prime	N	open cluster	0.4–0.8	N
M35	K2 C0	Y	open cluster	0.1–0.2	N
NGC 2158	K2 C0	Y	open cluster	1–2	N
M4	K2 C2	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
M80	K2 C2	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
Upper Scorpius	K2 C2, C15	N	association	≲0.01	Y
ρ Ophiuchus	K2 C2	N	open cluster	<0.01	N
Pleiades	K2 C4	N	open cluster	0.1–0.2	Y
Hyades	K2 C4, C13	N	open cluster	0.4–0.8	Y
M67	K2 C5, C16, C18	Y	open cluster	3–4	Y
Praesepe	K2 C5, C16, C18	N	open cluster	0.4–0.8	Y
Ruprecht 147	K2 C7	Y	open cluster	3–4	N
NGC 6717	K2 C7	N	globular cluster	≥11	N
NGC 6530	K2 C9	Y	open cluster	<0.01	N
M9	K2 C11	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
M19	K2 C11	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
NGC 6293	K2 C11	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
NGC 6355	K2 C11	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
Terzan 5	K2 C11	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N
NGC 1647	K2 C13	N	open cluster	0.1–0.2	N
NGC 1746	K2 C13	N	open cluster*	-	N
NGC 1817	K2 C13	N	open cluster	1–2	N
Taurus	K2 C13	N	association	<0.01	N
NGC 1750	K2 C13	N	open cluster	0.1–0.2	N
NGC 1758	K2 C13	N	open cluster	0.4–0.8	N
NGC 5897	K2 C15	Y	globular cluster	≥11	N

See talks by A. Miglio and Madeline Howell

& look also for TESS [bright stars]

open clusters spectroscopic studies: not only large surveys

SPA : Stellar Population Astrophysics

Large Program, *GIARPS*=*HARPS-N* (optical) + *GIANO-B* (IR)

at 3.54m 'Telescopio Nazionale Galileo' (TNG)

June 2018-November 2021

SPA PI: L. Origlia (SPA-OC: AB)

http://nisp.oabo.inaf.it/SPA_TNG_LP/

- *Giants & supergiants in young clusters and associations (also with high-extinction)*
- *Cepheids & Miras*
- *Open clusters in the Solar neighbourhood*

SPA-Open Clusters

*47 OCs observed 2018-2020
(results published for about ½)*

- *bright stars, not generally targeted in surveys*
- *a few stars in a large number of nearby OCs*
 - ➔ *metallicity [abundances]*
 - ➔ *ages (via stellar models)*
 - ➔ *distribution of metallicity, abundances*
(chemical map of disk, precise ages)
 - ➔ *elements not easily accessible (e.g. F, He)*
- *a few ten of stars in key clusters, MS & giants*
 - ➔ *detailed abundances*
 - ➔ *test of stellar models (diffusion, mixing)*
 - ➔ *test of homogeneity*
 - ➔ *test of all nucleosynthetic chains*
(chemical evolution)
 - ➔ *influence of activity, rotation, binarism*
- *Legacy value, also for large survey*

SPA-Open Clusters (main sequence stars)

[Frasca+2019](#) : ASCC 123

10 MS G-type stars
 $[Fe/H] = +0.21 \pm 0.01$

[D'Orazi+2020](#) : Praesepe

reddening map

[Alonso-Santiago+2021](#) : Stock 2

SPA-Open Clusters (giants / red clump stars)

[Casali+ 2020](#) : 4 OCs intermediate/old

[Zhang R.+2021](#) : 16 OCs, age ~ 100 Myr-1.5 Gyr

(near) future surveys of interest for stellar clusters

WEAVE : the next high-resolution spectroscopic survey in the Northern hemisphere

*WEAVE has ~1000 fibers
(plus 20 mIFUs, 1 lIFU)
@WHT, FoV 2 deg \emptyset
 $R \sim 5000$: 366-959 nm
 $R \sim 20000$: in 2 (of 3) WL regions*

*WEAVE due to start in H1 2022,
with 70% of WHT time for 5 yr*

*Will observe ~300 open clusters
plus SFR plus GCs*

Open time for ING participants

Jin, Trager, Dalton, et al. (to be submitted soon)

4MOST: the next high-resolution spectroscopic survey in the Southern hemisphere

*4MOST has ~2400 fibers
(1600 LR, 800 HR at same time)
@VISTA, FoV 4 sq.deg
 $R \sim 5000 + R \sim 20000$*

4MOST due to start in 2023 (??)

*Will (probably) observe "all"
open clusters and GCs
[proposal submitted, decision
expected before end 2021]*

5 year for the public survey

MOONS : a true friend in high-reddening regions

Courtesy E. Dalessandro

*MOONS has ~1000 fibers
@VLT, FoV 25 arcmin \emptyset
R~5000: 0.6-1.8 μ
R~9000: at CaT
R~20000: in H band*

MOONS due to start in 2024 (??)

*Will observe inner-MW/bulge
GCs, high-reddening disk clusters
(in GTO)*

*Open time for everyone,
ESO-style*

Thank you for your attention, and enjoy !

- *Lots of data already available, up for grabs*
- *Past, present & future is full of surveys (astro/photo/spectro/seismo/etc)*
- *Go get it, shake and stir with your own precious work: new use, new ideas welcome*

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